

COMPONENT APPROACH IN TEACHING WRITING FOR GRADUATE STUDENTS

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Annotation. From the viewpoint of foreign language teaching, some researchers believe that written speech performance, particularly speaking in a foreign language, is only illegal; however, another group of researchers disagrees, suggesting the term "expressive form of speech." Sharing the latter viewpoint, we believe that written speech is an expressive form of its two subtypes - reproductive and productive - coexisting. For the successful implementation of the process of writing competence, it is necessary to determine the optimal ratio of reproduction and its products, as well as to determine the characteristics of competence in each of these activities and take them into account in the learning process.

Keywords: Competency approach, graduate students, writing, developing writing ability.

INTRODUCTION

Scientist: "Productivity in foreign language teaching is a means of reproduction and the main goal of the development of communicative foreign language as a subject of learning a foreign language" [1]. We should try to make sure that students' speech is the result of productive thinking, their own creative activity, but we must not forget that it is very unlikely to achieve this goal without the participation of reproductive processes. At the same time, the process of producing other people's thoughts, and therefore reproductions, is natural in a real relationship, such as the creation of speech. The following criteria are used to classify the text only as secondary: - Representation; - Lack of evaluation of the original text; - Thematic unit of primary and secondary texts [2].

Considering this linguistic classification in terms of foreign language teaching, we note the following. In terms of content, all texts created by students can be divided into productive (expressing their thoughts without relying on the prototype text), reproductiveproductive (expressing one's own opinion, original, evaluation of the content of the main text), reproductive (providing information about the original). In addition to the content of the text being created, the process of reproduction may also be related to its form. At the same time, multiplication at the formal level can vary depending on the complete repetition of individual sentences and even superphrase homogeneity (which is often found in non-linguistic students' written texts in a foreign language), creative use of lexical and grammatical tools, structural and compositional features of the original text. In the first case, the process of content design is only reproductive, in the second case - reproductive-productive. Thus, when students create text, productive, reproductive-productive, and reproductive processes are possible both at the level of the content plan and at the level of the expression plan. Modern pedagogical science directs the learning process from knowledge to competence. They differ conceptually from each other. The competency approach has been shown to have the

following characteristics: - purposefulness; - project activity of the teacher, the content of which is a means to an end; - formation of competence in action (in our case in communication); - focus on independent learning and selfassessment; - implement the process on the basis of pedagogical and information technologies; - focus on situational learning. The main issues in the teaching of foreign languages in the education system of Uzbekistan are the modernization of the scientific and methodological system of education, improving the level of professional education, adapting to the global educational space.

The writer tried to increase the students' writing mastery through the method the product oriented approach. Based on the background, the writer wrote a dissertation paper entitled: "*Competency approach in teaching writing for graduates*". The reasons why the writer used this method were as follows: a) the writer interested in writing skills; b) teachers felt confused to choose appropriate writing methods.

Formulation of the research questions in this research were:

What are the advantages of competent approach in developing writing ability and motivating graduate learners?

What problems and types of errors do usually annoy graduate learners in writing?

What are the principles of competent approach in classroom?

What are university teachers' beliefs and practices on the opposed approaches in writing course?

In which age/level competent approach might be presented on writing skills?

Competent approach would seem to be the ideal way in which students could use their English creatively which different levels might find themselves and to practice and develop their writing skill. For these reasons, the researcher is interested in analyzing the use of competent approach in teaching writing for the students of the fourth course. The researcher also wants to know the advantages and the problems encountered by learners and teachers in using it.

The purpose of the study was to find out the effectiveness of competent approach on improving learners' writing abilities.

The **basic goal** of this research was to identify how graduate learners can improve their writing skills by using competent approach in the class settings.

Based on the explanation above the writer would like to propose the **hypothesis** as follow: The students who are taught through competent techniques achieve better than students who are taught process approach.

In order to realize expected hypothesis and achieve the basic goal, the researcher set out a sequence of objectives. The objective of this study is fivefold:

-To describe the CA (Competent approach) implementation to improve graduates' writing skill.

-To put into practice CA as an effective technique for EFL learners;

-To find out which students have trouble with writing acquisition;

-To identify how students' writing skill improved after being taught by using CA.

-To provide the questionnaires on the usage and reactions on CA.

METHODOLOGY OF RESEARCH

The method of research gives the readers detailed information about how the study was conducted. This information pertains to the following specific aspects of the study: a) the subjects, b) the materials, c) the procedures, and d) the analyses.

Setting of the study

The study was conducted at the USWLU among the fourth year learners whose English competence is of almost mixed levels. Almost all of these students studied English by process approach which focuses on grammar, vocabulary and reading. Therefore their communicative competence of all skills, especially writing is limited.

Subjects

The study was conducted at university with the 4th year learners. 24 students in total and three teachers were involved in the research as collaborators. This research is a survey research because it uses questionnaires to gather information, as well as the researcher observes the learners' writing acquisition. Questionnaires are planned to explore students and teachers' attitude towards CA.

In this dissertation research the researchers' basic role is to be a teacher and observer whilst the action. Furthermore, the writer also collects and analyzes data then reporting the results of study.

The subjects were two groups of higher education system. Both groups consisted of 12 students who studied English for over ten years. All the subjects were native speakers of Uzbek language and they were taught by the same researcher during the practical period. Nevertheless, according to the given information by their home teacher, both groups have multilevel nature, the level of students' proficiency in English ranged from intermediate+ to upper intermediate. Its multi-level nature could make the researcher to anticipate some problems with the performance of the tasks.

Group 407 was selected as experimental group, as for group 408 stood as control group.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The present research work focuses on identifying the difficulties of the students which they face on producing a piece of work in the classes and determining the efficiency of product approach applied in a range of stages in teaching writing. Additionally, she prepared special questions for experiential group concerning the reason of learning Writing, the achievements that they faced while writing a various forms. Then three teachers from this establishment attended in questionnaire sharing their views with the researcher.

To reach her hypothesis the researcher provided detailed statistical survey while calculating the results of pre and post test results. The purpose of a statistical study is to answer research questions, and by collecting relevant and meaningful data, a researcher can find patterns that help her answer questions and support her conclusion. These correlated data help the researcher explain the results of study to readers and help the readers picture the patters that the researcher has found.

Correlated data can be presented either as descriptive statistics and graphic representations. Both groups have the same form of pre-test, the researcher prepared ten different variants of pre-assignment in one hour and twenty minutes. She checked short story according to the following criteria: *Grammar* – 0 – 20 %, *Vocabulary* – 0 – 20 %, *Mechanics* – 0 – 20 %, *Fluency* – 0 – 20 %, *Organization* – 0 – 20 %. So the total should be 100 %.

While making a comparison between two groups' results, it is visible below that the experiential group achieved better results. Three people in this group got higher scores. In control group the only member was able to get more than 72%, their average grade was 50%.

Only six participants showed the worst trend in this statistical calculation achieving elementary level.

In a statistical study, when measurements of subjects' behavior and performance are taken and represented numerically, there tends to be a central numerical point around which most of the scores are clustered. This phenomenon is known as the central tendency. Central tendency is commonly indicated in three ways- as a mean, a mode and median.

The mean is the average numerical value in a set of numerical values. The mean is calculated by adding up all of the values in the set and then dividing the sum by the number of values in the set. So the mean of EG will be 64. The mean of CG is $658/12 \approx 55$.

The mode is simply the numerical value that occurs most frequently in a set of numerical values, and it is found by counting the number of times that each value in the set occurs. As shown in Table on pre test results of CG is 57, but EG had the mode of 67.

In a set of numerical values, the median is the value at the center of the range of the set- half of values in the set are equal to or above the median and half of the values are equal to or below the median. The set scores of both contain 12 scores, the middle scores in the range are 75 and 69; and there are five scores equal to, so the median of EG will be 72. But in control group a set of scores were to have an equal twelve number of scores, too, in such case the researcher added the two middle scores and divided them by two. In this case the median for this set is $72+57/2 \approx 65$.

While the central tendency focuses on what is typical about group's behavior and performance, dispersion focuses on the behavior of the individuals in the group. There are two indicators of individual; behavior: range and standard deviation.

In a set of scores, the range is the number of points between the highest and lowest scores in the set, plus 1. To find the range, the researcher subtracted the lowest score from the highest score and added 1. So, the range of EG is $80-45+1=36$. The range of CG will be $72-40+1=33$.

The standard deviation is the average of the differences of all the scores from the mean. To calculate it, the researcher began subtracting the mean from each score in the set. Then squared each of these values and added them up. He divided the total by the number of scores, and squared root of that total would be SD.

CONCLUSION

In this experiment as a researcher I tried to discuss more on the situation and causes of the problems occurred in the writing practice through competency and process oriented approach. I found that problems of EFL learners of the UzSWLU lie mostly in written assignments. The detailed analysis of these errors also shows that the learners' most important source of errors is unawareness of the rules can be considered as the origin. Therefore, in order to improve the spelling and writing ability of the learners, teachers should pay sometimes attention to the use of necessary approach on its place. To meet this purpose, two opposite approaches like product and process approaches can be helpful. Teachers have to be encouraged and provided with opportunities to conduct classroom-based research so that they can experiment with a wider range of error feedback strategies to find out what works best in their own context. For teachers who don't feel uncomfortable in the role of occasional composer, have a commitment toward enjoying the time spent with students, reducing the number of common errors they make, and improving their English writing ability.

The ultimate goal in writing a text is to develop a cohesive and coherent discourse according to its context of use; however, this does not relegate the crucial role of its linguistic building blocks including grammar, vocabulary, and mechanics of writing and so on. One of the insurmountable problems FL learners encounter is the acquisition of the relationship between forms and functions which cannot be obtained overnight. Although teachers of writing should emphasize the one-to-one non correspondence between forms and functions, it is the responsibility of teachers of grammar, vocabulary and other sub/skills as well to elaborate on them from the outset of language learning. Teachers can diagnose these inappropriate uses of elements through the students' writing practice

In order to learn more about L2 writers' use of language in the process writing, we need to apply to L2 writing the research methods. We also need to understand how students compose in both their native languages and in English to understand more about their learning strategies, the role of translation, and transfer of skills.

Finally, our research determines learners' cognitive processes and language awareness through writing product and writing process both separately and combined. Also concerning participants' writing process and their final product, there are some patterns which enable us to group participants into certain profiles. It cannot be denied that they are useful and effective tools that should be applied in any class. The use of feedback in learning acquisition is a way to make the lessons more interesting, enjoyable and effective in terms of process oriented approach.

Furthermore, the whole process of conducting this research and collecting data and teaching them has contributed to my professional development in terms of providing me with knowledge of the varied current issues and strategies in teaching writing. It has really enriched my theoretical background, and enhanced my ability to teach writing effectively.

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